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The Management and Development of Tista Rural Tourism as Alternative Tourism in Tabanan, Bali Indonesia

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Abstract

The development of rural tourism as alternative tourism arises from the concept of sustainable tourism development, where the development of rural tourism is expected to be able to preserve nature, the environment, culture, and all other resources in accordance with their carrying capacity. The people of Tista Village strongly support the management and development of rural tourism because the various benefits felt by the community are related to the harmonization of community life, quality of community life, environmental quality, cultural and spiritual quality which are increasingly becoming real benefits of developing rural tourism. These situations and phenomena make rural tourism an alternative in creating and supporting quality community-based tourism towards responsible tourism. Quantitative descriptive methods with Likert Scale Analysis and Importance Performance Analysis (IPA) were used to find the development of the Tista Rural Tourism as alternative tourism in Tabanan Regency and to create a quality and sustainable rural tourism. The results of the analysis of community responses related to Tista Rural Tourism as alternative tourism in Tabanan Regency, the overall average value of the importance level is 4,72 (very important) and the overall average value of the performance level is 4,10 (good), where the results grouping of 36 indicators in each quadrant, namely: the main priority quadrant as many as 7 indicators, the superiority quadrant as many as 16 indicators, the low priority quadrant as many as 9 indicators, and the excess resources quadrant as many as 4 indicators.

Keywords: Rural Tourism Development, Alternative Tourism, Community-Based Rural Tourism, Sustainable Rural Tourism

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

The development of the tourism sector which is in line with the bottom up planning model is the resource community base management model or community-based tourism (Korten, 1986). One of the community-based tourism developments is the development of rural tourism. The community-based tourism paradigm has long been an alternative paradigm to conventional tourism which has many weaknesses due to the tendency towards physical development and lack of attention to socio-cultural problems of the community, so that villages that have their own uniqueness and distinctiveness are starting to be looked at to become rural tourism or village tourism by the government and tourism actors.

A rural tourism is a village area that offers an overall atmosphere that reflects the authenticity of the countryside, both from socio-economic life, socio-culture, daily customs, building architecture and typical village spatial structures or unique and interesting economic activities and has the potential to develop various types of tourism component (attractions, accommodation, food, beverages, etc.). The characteristics of a rural tourism are the authenticity, uniqueness, local taste, and regional pride, as well as the quality of life of the people. (Nasikum, 1997; Fagence, 1997 in Antara & Arida, 2015).

The development of rural tourism as alternative tourism arises from the concept of sustainable tourism development, where the development of rural tourism is expected to be able to preserve nature, the environment, culture, and all other resources in accordance with their carrying capacity. In the last decade, many developing countries have paid special attention to the tourism industry, it is only a pity that many programs are planned but not carefully considered, whether the benefits to be gained are greater than the damage that may be caused.

Matters related to the success of tourism development can be divided into three main factors, namely: 1) Internal factors, classified as: regional potential, environmental preservation, and participation of local residents; 2) External factors are key factors, such as: the concern of tourists for environmental sustainability, research activities in alternative tourism development areas, as well as local communities; and 3) Structural factors are institutions and policies in alternative tourism development areas at local, national and international levels. Inaccuracies in managing and planning tourism resources can affect their quality and sustainability as well as benefits for the community, which will not be in accordance with the goals and targets.

Approaches in developing rural tourism which are friendly to nature, social, culture, and people's economy, are: 1) *Holistic Approach*, which sees holistically the dimensions of development that integrates development elements in an integrated manner whose problem solving is carried out collectively and participatively; 2) *Participatory Learning*, where the learning or education process in the management and development of rural tourism is local actors in this case are the community and supported by the local government because the people who understand the problems related to the development of rural tourism are themselves; 3) *Empowerment of Management*, where strengthening empowerment through strong institutions will provide improved performance in the management and development of rural tourism; 4) *Action Research*, where real action is needed in its management and development, so that it can provide benefits to the environment. Applied research is needed in assisting the quality and capacity improvement of rural tourism management; and 5) *Synergy and Network*, where the willingness to open a network to realize the duties and responsibilities in facing the challenges of management and development together to create a balance, so that trust is built among the actors of rural tourism development (Baiquni, 2010).

One of the rural tourism whose management and development receives support from the community is Tista Rural Tourism, which is located in Kerambitan District, Tabanan Regency. Tista Village consists of four hamlets/banjars, namely: Dangin Pangkung Hamlet, Dauh Pangkung Hamlet, Carik Hamlet, and Lebah Hamlet. It is located in a slightly undulating lowland area, especially in the southern and western part of the village. Tista Village is an agricultural area where most of the population consists of farmers working in rice fields. The communities strongly maintain the traditions of their ancestors, respect their natural environment, as well as their culture, so that the harmonization of people's lives is seen as very prominent in social life. Tista Rural Tourism was used as a research location because it is one of the Advanced Rural Tourism in Tabanan Regency, with excellent level of tourism awareness and community enthusiasm in building and developing their village, on the other hand the area of Tista Village is very vulnerable to property development, where the location is very strategic close to urban areas.

The diverse tourism potential in the Tista Rural Tourism can be developed into tourist attractions, such as: natural potential (rice fields, natural scenery with the background of Mount Batukaru, sunset and sunrise), cultural potential (Andir Dance which only exists in Tista Village), culinary potential (*kaliadrem* snacks, purple sweet potato steamed *apem* cake, rice mixed with Balinese spices and filled with side dishes such as tempeh, tofu, egg, and sambal which is called *nasi bejek*, lemongrass jamu/herb), spiritual potential (Beji Temple with its spring which is believed to cure disease, Celagi Temple which is also believed to be a place to ask for healing, Batu Gede which is believed to be the centre power of Tista Village). These potentials can be enjoyed by tourists when

traveling in Tista Rural Tourism. This village was designated as a rural tourism by the Regent of Tabanan Number: 180/319/03/HK & HAM/2016, 26 October 2016, where previously the Pokdarwis of Tista Rural Tourism was also established by the Regent of Tabanan Number: 180/27403/HK & HAM/2016, 19 September 2016.

The people of Tista Village strongly support the management and development of their village into a rural tourism because the various benefits felt by the community are related to the harmonization of community life, cleanliness and orderliness of the village face, road infrastructure as community economic access is concerned by the government, chance to receive various training related to tourism, growth of community activity and entrepreneurial spirit. With the development of the Tista Rural Tourism, the quality of community life, environmental quality, cultural and spiritual quality is increasing which is a real benefit of developing a rural tourism. These situations and phenomena make rural tourism an alternative to creating and supporting quality community-based tourism towards responsible tourism. So that, the research question of the study is what is the community's response to the Tista tourist village as an alternative tourism in Tabanan Regency.

1.2. Literature Review

1.2.1. Development Rural Tourism

According to Pitana (2005), rural tourism is a village area with an atmosphere that overall reflects the authenticity of the village atmosphere in the spatial structure, building architecture, as well as the socio-cultural life of the community, and is able to provide components of basic needs such as accommodation, food and beverages, souvenirs, and tourist attractions for tourists.

Based on Legislation Number 10 of 2009 concerning Tourism, people who are in tourism areas get roles and priorities to become workers or laborers, share as well as carry out the management. In the development of a rural tourism, the role of the community is needed so that the implementation of the development is sustainable so that the rural tourism can be developed. The rural tourism is an alternative tourism which uses community life as an attraction, so that the level of involvement of the local community is high and can be accounted for from social and environmental aspects.

According to Pearce (1995) in Aliyah, et al. (2020), it is stated that the development of rural tourism is defined as efforts to complete and improve tourism facilities to meet the needs of tourists. In the development of rural tourism, there are two approaches that need to be considered, namely: 1) Community-based tourism development, where tourism development focuses on improving the welfare of the community, where these activities are carried out, operated, managed, and coordinated by the community. Community empowerment needs to be based on the following things: improving people's living standards, increasing the level of income economically as well as equitable distribution of local people's income, developing small and medium scale businesses, developing a competitive and cooperative spirit, utilizing tourism as optimally as possible as an agent that contributes to tradition and culture by minimal impact and 2) Sustainable tourism development, where tourism development balances three aspects, namely: economy, environment, and society. Sustainable tourism development has main objective of improving the quality of life, strengthening values and society, and providing added value to the community's economy.

1.2.2. Alternative Tourism Concept

Based on the destination life cycle introduced by Butler (1980), the polarized debate revolves around "impact" which initiates the search for lower-impact forms of tourism that are more inclusive and appropriate. Finally, alternative tourism forms of mass tourism were found which were interpreted as tourism that was more authentic, least dangerous, community focused, and developmental balance based. Alternative tourism has a pedigree in the global movement of the 1980s that aimed to bring the "environment" to the centre of the development dialogue.

The alternative development approach is considered as a response to the failure of conventional development patterns in solving the problem of poverty. Poverty is considered as a condition of relative disempowerment in

relation to the opportunities of each household as the basis of social power. It is further assumed that the occurrence of underdevelopment of a community is not caused by the ignorance and incompetence of the community but is the result of the inability of the community to the structural pressures caused by the growth development model that ignores human rights. In addition, efforts are needed to change the structure that makes people powerless and build a development model with the principles of democracy, economic growth that guarantees the interests of the community (appropriate economic growth), gender equality, and intergeneration equity (Suparjan) and Hempri Suyatno, 2003: 4).

In more detail, Midgley defines social development as an alternative development: "...to result in the fulfilment of people's aspirations for personal achievement and happiness, to promote a proper adjustment between individuals and their communities, to foster freedom and security and to engender a sense of belonging and social propose", which means: "social development is a development activity that results in the fulfilment of citizens' desires for individual happiness and achievement, develops appropriate self-adjustment between individuals and their communities, creates freedom and security and creates a sense of belonging and social planning" (James Midgley, 1995).

Thus, alternative tourism is a form of tourism whose development is small in scale, all of its activities involve the community, which does not damage the environment, is consistent with the values of nature conservation, social, and cultural values of the community, and makes it possible for local communities and tourists to enjoy a positive and natural interaction that is carried out in an area that is not developing too quickly and gains depth of meaning and the beauty of various experiences.

Some of the characteristics of alternative tourism, namely: small scale, local ownership, low density, under local communities control, long term orientation, harmonization and welfare of local communities emphasis, no dominant market, complementing existing activities, tourists with individual or small group arrangements, low leakage rate, multiplier effect (Butler, 1992 and Weaver, 1993).

1.2.3. Community-Based Tourism Concept

The quality tourism model emphasizes the importance of community-based development, bottom-up development and locality, which is based on a motivation to develop and encourage community structures to strengthen empowerment, local level development, and integrate with local culture. Development policies must be able to create harmonization of society with the environment which has long been fused with ecological values. In this context, society becomes the subject of development while maintaining rooted values, social structures and cultural traditions of the community.

Alternative development models emphasize participatory and fulfilment of basic needs and human rights. Participatory development emphasizes broad participation, accessibility, community representation in the planning and decision-making processes that affect their fate, while development emphasizes the fulfilment of basic needs and human rights emphasizes development to meet three basic needs of society, namely: welfare, freedom, and identity (Johan Galtung, 1980).

According to Murphy (1988), community empowerment in tourism development views that the development of tourism activities is a community-based activity, where physical and non-physical elements (tradition and culture) are always attached to the community which is the main driving element of tourism activity itself. The principles of community empowerment, namely: 1) Enabling: creating an atmosphere or climate that allows the potential of the community to develop; 2) Empowering: strengthening the potential or power possessed by the community; and 3) Protecting: preventing unequal competition and exploitation of the strong against the weak.

1.3. Research Methodology

The research method used in this research is quantitative descriptive method. The sampling technique was proportionate stratified random sampling, that is: a sampling technique by taking into account a level (class) in the

population element in this case the people of Tista Village, Tabanan Regency. Researchers have determined to get a sample of 100 respondents. Data collection methods used in this study were observation, questionnaires, and literature study.

To analyse the data, Likert Scale was used to measure the attitude or opinion of the Tista community towards an alternative tourism phenomenon. The answer to each instrument item had a scale from very good to very bad. With Likert Scale, the variables to be measured are defined into indicators and then used as a starting point for compiling instrument items which can be in the form of statements or questions. The following is the scale used in this study: a. Very Bad, b. Not Good, c. Fairly Good, d. Good, e. Very Good (Sugiyono, 2013).

Importance Performance Analysis (IPA) is also used to measure the attributes of importance and performance levels that are useful for the development of Tista Rural Tourism as alternative tourism in Tabanan Regency. The total assessment of the level of importance and the level of performance of each indicator is obtained by adding up the results by multiplying the scores of each scale with the number of respondents who chose on Likert Scale, then the average value of the level of importance and performance is analysed on the Importance-Performance Matrix, which The X axis represents activity, while the Y axis represents expectations (Rahardipha et al., 2016). Then there will be results in the form of four quadrants according to Table 1.

Table 1: the Form of four quadrants

A = Top Priority	B = Maintain Achievement
C = Low Priority	D = Excessive

Picture. *Importance Performance Analysis (IPA) Quadrant*

The interpretation of each of these quadrants are:

Top Priority

In this quadrant there are factors that are considered important and expected but the performance or activity is not satisfying, so concentration is needed to allocate resources to improve performance in this quadrant.

Maintain Achievement

In this quadrant there are factors that are considered important and expected by the community as alternative tourism, so it is mandatory to maintain these performance achievements.

Low Priority

In this quadrant there are factors that are considered to have low performance or activity and are also not very important, so there is no need to prioritize or pay more attention to these factors.

Excessive

In this quadrant there are factors that are considered not too important by the community but the resulting performance is very good. Therefore, the level of importance is small and the activity is very good, so this quadrant is considered as an excessive group in terms of resources.

Table 2: Alternative tourism variables and indicators used in this study

Variables	Indicators	
Small Scale	A1	Limited number of tourists

Variables	Indicators	
	A2	Specific area settings
	A3	Type of attraction set
	A4	Time duration set
	A5	Provided an understanding of the area visited
Involving the Community	B1	Provided Local Guide
	B2	Community Training
	B3	Socialization in the Community
	B4	The community is involved in the management of the rural tourism
	B5	The community prepare homestay
	B6	The community concern about rural tourism
Nature, Social, Culture Conservation	C1	Long Term Orientation
	C2	Harmonization of Community Life
	C3	The contribution of tourism to socio-culture
	C4	Tourism's contribution to nature
	C5	Environmental hygiene and sanitation
	C6	Waste management
	C7	Maintaining clean water sources
	C8	Maintaining community sources of livelihood
	C9	Safety and security in the rural tourism
Positive Interaction Between Community and Tourist	D1	Quality of relationship between host and guest
	D2	Tourists stay on homestay
	D3	People feel comfortable with tourist arrivals
	D4	Tourists respect customs in rural tourism
	D5	Communities benefit from tourist arrivals
Reasonable Development	E1	Complementing existing facilities
	E2	Using local materials in the construction of tourism facilities
	E3	Building with local labour and simple equipment
	E4	The development carried out through planning process
	E5	The development carried out is socialized in the community
	E6	The development carried out is beneficial to the community
	E7	The development carried out does not damage nature and the environment
Meaning and Experience	F1	Tourists are considered as friends and relatives
	F2	Tourists are introduced to the local life of the community
	F3	Local tourism activities offered to tourists
	F4	Local menu offered to tourists

Source: Research Questionnaire (2022)

2. Results and Discussions

This research will describe the Importance Level Analysis, Performance Level Analysis, and IPA Analysis related to the development of alternative tourism in Tista Rural Tourism, Kerambitan District, Tabanan Regency. The following is the explanation of each of these analyses.

2.1 Importance Level Analysis of Alternative Tourism in Tista Rural

Based on the data collected from the responses of the people of Tista Rural Tourism and through analytical calculations, it was found that the average level of importance of Tista Rural Tourism as alternative tourism in Tabanan Regency was 4.72 which could be categorized as very important, which means that the community's response regarding the importance level of Tista Rural Tourism as alternative tourism is categorized as very important. In detail, the highest to lowest average results are related to the importance level, namely: Positive interaction between the community and tourists (4.87; very important), Reasonable development (4.80; very important), Nature, social, and cultural preservation (4.78; very important), Involving the community (4.76; very important), Small scale (4.58; very important), and Meaning and experience (4.51; very important).

These results can also be interpreted that, of the 6 (six) factors used to assess the importance level aspect, it turns out that there are 4 (four) factors that are above the average and 2 (two) other factors below the average. The four factors that are above the average aspect of interest are positive interaction between the community and tourists, reasonable development, nature conservation, social, culture, and community involvement.

When referring to the goal of developing the Tista Rural Tourism as alternative tourism in Tabanan Regency, the most important thing to focus on is "positive interaction between the community and tourists." Real efforts that can be implemented are to improve the quality of the familial relationship between hosts and tourists, tourists are expected to stay at homestays, people feel comfortable with tourist arrivals, tourists respect customs in rural tourism, and people benefit from tourist arrivals in rural tourism. This is very necessary for increasing tourist satisfaction in Tista Rural Tourism because tourists and hosts will feel that they need each other, so that the services provided are the best services same as serving relatives or close relatives. Psychologically, tourists will feel like at home and with their own families which will have a positive effect on the impression and information given by tourists to their families, relatives, or friends which will be an effective promotion tool for Tista Rural Tourism, while on the community side, they will certainly be very supportive in the development of Tista Rural Tourism by actively participating in providing the best service and preserving the Tista Rural Tourism.

The second factor that is very important according to the community and above the average value of importance level is "Reasonable development." There are several concrete steps that can be taken, such as complementing existing facilities, building tourist facilities by utilizing local materials, building with local labour and simple equipment, the development carried out through the planning process, the development carried out previously disseminated to the community, the development carried out beneficial for the community, and the development carried out does not damage nature and the environment. The development in rural tourism is expected to be beneficial for the community by not sacrificing existing and productive lands, so that the community still has land to be processed as their livelihood which in its implementation requires planning and through an open process involving the whole community in its planning and implementation to minimize negative impact.

The third factor which is also very important for the community is "Natural, social, cultural preservation." The concrete efforts made are the harmonization of community life, the contribution of tourism to socio-culture, the contribution of tourism to nature, environmental hygiene and sanitation, waste and waste management, maintaining clean water sources, maintaining community livelihood sources, safety and security in a rural tourism. The management and development of the Tista Rural Tourism will strengthen the preservation of nature, social and culture of the community. The customs and traditions in society which are inherited from the Ancestors become the unifier and binder of the Tista people's social life which until now has been strongly intertwined, so that the harmonization and kinship of community life are very high.

The fourth factor that becomes very important is "Involving the community." This is done with some efforts, such as: preparing local guides, training for the community, socialization to the community, the community is involved in managing the rural tourism, the community prepare homestay, and the community concern about the rural tourism. The essence of the management and development of the Tista Rural Tourism is the involvement and active participation of the Tista community. This can be proven by the full support of the Tista community for the development of the Tista Rural Tourism, where the result is that Tista Rural Tourism becomes one of the "advanced category" rural tourism in Tabanan Regency. Community businesses and activities are very active in carrying out the work programs of the Tista Rural Tourism. The community principle is if the village is clean, healthy, safe, beautiful, then the community will be happy and peaceful living in it, so that tourists who come to visit will feel the same way.

2.2 Performance Level Analysis of Alternative Tourism in Tista Rural Tourism

From the results of the questionnaire related to the responses of the Tista community, in general, the average performance of Tista Rural Tourism as alternative tourism in Tabanan Regency is 4.10 which can be categorized as good, which means this number is lower than the results of the importance level of Tista Rural Tourism as alternative tourism. in Tabanan Regency. In general, it can be seen that each factor the average value is in the good category. As for the 6 (six) factors used to measure the performance results, there is an average value, such as: Participating in the community (4.18; good), Reasonable development (4.18; good), Conservation of nature, social, culture (4.13; good), Meaning and experience (4.10; good), Positive interaction between the community and tourists (4.03; good), and Small scale (3.92; good).

It can also be explained that there are 4 (four) factors that score above the overall average and 2 (two) factors that score below the overall average. Factor values that are above the overall average value, namely: Involving the community, reasonable development, nature, social, culture conservation, and meaning and experience. The interpretation that can be analysed from these findings, it turns out that small-scale factors and positive interaction factors of the community and tourists are still below the overall average value, which means that Tista Rural Tourism activities are still oriented on a large scale in receiving tourist visits but there has not been a positive interaction between the community and tourists, so it is necessary to arrange visits and tourist activities as well as improve the hospitality of the community in providing services to tourists who come to the Tista Rural Tourism. In this way, the quality or benefits of community interaction with tourists can be obtained, so that the quality of management and development of the Tista Rural Tourism is also better.

Table 3: Analysis of the Level of Performance and Level of Interest of Tista Rural Tourism as Alternative Tourism in Tabanan Regency

Variables	Indicators		Rural Tourism Performance	Importance	Performance Category	Importance Category
Small Scale	A1	Limited number of tourists	3,76	4,26	Good	Very Important
	A2	Specific area settings	4,10	4,44	Good	Very Important
	A3	Type of attraction set	3,92	4,64	Good	Very Important
	A4	Time duration set	3,72	4,58	Good	Very Important
	A5	Provided an understanding of the area visited	4,08	5,00	Good	Very Important
	Average		3,92	4,58	Good	Very Important
Involving the Community	B1	Provided Local Guide	4,40	4,58	Very Good	Very Important
	B2	Community Training	4,26	4,88	Very Good	Very Important
	B3	Socialization to the Community	4,34	4,88	Very Good	Very Important

Variables	Indicators		Rural Tourism Performance	Importance	Performance Category	Importance Category
	B4	The community is involved in the management of the rural tourism	4,22	4,78	Very Good	Very Important
	B5	The community prepare homestay	3,72	4,50	Good	Very Important
	B6	The community concern about rural tourism	4,14	4,92	Good	Very Important
	Average		4,18	4,76	Good	Very Important
Nature, Social, Culture Conservation	C1	Long Term Orientation	3,94	4,78	Good	Very Important
	C2	Harmonization of Community Life	4,42	4,96	Very Good	Very Important
	C3	The contribution of tourism to socio-culture	3,98	4,70	Good	Very Important
	C4	Tourism's contribution to nature	4,18	4,56	Good	Very Important
	C5	Environmental hygiene and sanitation	3,96	4,76	Good	Very Important
	C6	Waste and waste management	3,78	4,72	Good	Very Important
	C7	Maintaining clean water sources	4,44	4,88	Very Good	Very Important
	C8	Maintaining community sources of livelihood	4,18	4,82	Good	Very Important
	C9	Safety and security in the rural tourism	4,26	4,88	Very Good	Very Important
	Average		4,13	4,78	Good	Very Important
Positive Interaction Between Community and Tourist	D1	Quality of relationship between host and guest	4,16	4,82	Good	Very Important
	D2	Tourists stay in homestay	3,54	4,78	Good	Very Important
	D3	People feel comfortable with tourist arrivals	4,00	4,94	Good	Very Important
	D4	Tourists respect customs in rural tourism	4,14	4,90	Good	Very Important
	D5	Communities benefit from tourist arrivals	4,32	4,90	Very Good	Very Important
	Average		4,03	4,87	Good	Very Important
Reasonable Development	E1	Complementing existing facilities	3,82	4,58	Good	Very Important
	E2	Using local materials in the construction of tourism facilities	4,04	4,86	Good	Very Important
	E3	Building with local labour and simple equipment	4,20	4,80	Good	Very Important
	E4	The development carried out through planning process	4,24	4,84	Very Good	Very Important

Variables	Indicators		Rural Tourism Performance	Importance	Performance Category	Importance Category
	E5	The development carried out is socialized to the community	4,22	4,80	Very Good	Very Important
	E6	The development carried out is beneficial to the community	4,44	4,84	Very Good	Very Important
	E7	The development carried out does not damage nature and the environment	4,30	4,88	Very Good	Very Important
	Average		4,18	4,80	Good	Very Important
Meaning and Experience	F1	Tourists are considered as friends and relatives	4,08	4,60	Good	Very Important
	F2	Tourists are introduced to the local life of the community	4,06	4,46	Good	Very Important
	F3	Local tourism activities offered to tourists	4,02	4,48	Good	Very Important
	F4	Local menu offered to tourists	4,22	4,48	Very Good	Very Important
	Average		4,10	4,51	Good	Very Important
	Overall Average		4,10	4,72	Good	Very Important

Source: Research Analysis Results (2022)

2.2.1. Gap Analysis of Tista Rural Tourism as Alternative Tourism in Tabanan Regency

This analysis is used to see the gap between the level of importance and performance on the six variables of Tista Rural Tourism as alternative tourism in Tabanan Regency. The smaller the gap between interest and performance, the better the application of alternative tourism in the Tista Rural Tourism, Tabanan Regency. Looking at the results of the average gap of Tista Rural Tourism as alternative tourism in Tabanan Regency, it was found that there were 3 (three) variables whose average Importance Performance Analysis (IPA) value was higher than the average value of importance and performance. These variables are community involvement, nature, social, culture preservation, and natural development. It means that those are the variables with the highest value compared to other variables.

In more detail regarding the gap between the importance and performance of the Tista Rural Tourism as alternative tourism in Tabanan Regency seen from the overall average value of the importance level is 4.72 which is categorized as very important and the overall average value of the performance level is 4.10 which is categorized as good, namely: 1) Involving the Community with importance level value 4.76 which is a very important category and the performance level value 4.18 which is a good category; 2) Preservation of Nature, Social and Culture with level of importance value 4.78 which is a very important category and performance level value 4.13 which is a good category; and 3) Reasonable Development with an importance level value 4.80 which is a very important category and a performance level value 4.18 which is a good category.

Figure 1: Gap Analysis in Tista Rural Tourism

Tista Rural Tourism as alternative tourism in Tabanan Regency is strongly supported by the community with active community involvement in its management and development. This is clearly seen at the importance level as an alternative tourism category that is very important and is supported by performance as alternative tourism with good category. Through the implementation, it proves that Tista Rural Tourism applies alternative tourism concepts in its development. It was mentioned earlier that there are 3 (three) important variables that are highly emphasized by the people of Tista Village in the development of Tista Rural Tourism as alternative tourism. Those are community involvement, nature, social and cultural preservation, and reasonable development. These three variables are also above the overall average value of the importance level and above the overall average value of the performance level.

This indicates that the Tista Rural Tourism community cares about the sustainability of their village in the development of rural tourism by playing an active role in the management and development as well as being a control towards a quality and sustainable rural tourism and improving community welfare based on a harmonious life full of kinship and mutual cooperation in Tista Rural Tourism Tabanan Regency.

2.3 Importance Performance Analysis (IPA) Tista Rural Tourism as Alternative Tourism in Tabanan Regency

The next analysis regarding Tista Rural Tourism as an alternative tourism in Tabanan Regency will be explained in relation to the results of the Importance Performance Analysis (IPA). IPA analysis is used to analyse how much expectations have been met and how much performance to meet these expectations has been implemented. Related to Tista Rural Tourism as alternative tourism in Tabanan Regency, IPA analysis will group 36 indicators to identify alternative tourism in Tista Rural Tourism, Tabanan Regency into a Cartesian Diagram.

Identification using IPA analysis in Tista Rural Tourism is grouped into 4 (four) Quadrants (A/I), (B/II), (C/III), and (D/IV). Each quadrant has a different meaning. Quadrant A is the main priority, Quadrant B is superiority, Quadrant C is a low priority, and Quadrant D is an excess resources.

2.3.2. Superiority

The superiority quadrant is quadrant that includes alternative tourism indicators in Tista Rural Tourism, Tabanan Regency which are considered important and expected by the community, simply this superiority quadrant means that the average value of each importance indicator is higher than the value of overall factor of importance level and the average value of each performance indicator is also higher than the average value of the overall factor of importance level.

All indicators in the superiority quadrant should be maintained because in this quadrant, there are accomplishments that have been achieved and need to be maintained to alternative tourism in Tista Rural Tourism, Tabanan Regency. There are 16 indicators for alternative tourism in the superiority quadrant. For more details, indicators including the superiority of Tista Rural Tourism as alternative tourism in Tabanan Regency can be seen as follows.

1. B2 : Community Training
2. B3 : Socialization to the community
3. B4 : The community is involved in the management of the rural tourism
4. B6 : The community concern about rural tourism
5. C2 : Harmonization of Community Life
6. C7 : Maintaining clean water sources
7. C8 : Maintaining community sources of livelihood
8. C9 : Safety and security in the rural tourism
9. D1 : Quality of Relationship between host and guest
10. D4 : Tourists respect customs in rural tourism
11. D5 : Community benefit from tourist arrivals
12. E3 : Building with local labor and simple equipment
13. E4 : The development is carried out through planning process
14. E5 : The development carried out is socialized to the community
15. E6 : The development carried out is beneficial to the community
16. E7 : The development carried out does not damage nature and the environment

2.3.3. Low Priority

In this quadrant, the community considers that alternative tourism indicators in Tista Rural Tourism, Tabanan Regency are considered less important, including their performance also receives less attention. This means that the quality of alternative tourism performance is low and the aspect of its importance to the community is low. This low priority quadrant shows that the average value of each importance indicator of is lower than the value of the overall factor of importance level and the average value of each performance indicator is also lower than the average value of the overall factor of importance level.

Indicators that are in the low priority quadrant have little influence on the community because they are not too important, so that the implementation of activities to realize alternative tourism in Tista Rural Tourism, Tabanan Regency on this indicator is not urgently pursued. However, vigilance and professionalism in the management of rural tourism require evaluation and control of the indicators in this quadrant.

Based on the results of the Cartesian diagram analysis, there are 9 indicators that are classified as low priority. For more details, the low priority of Tista Rural Tourism as alternative tourism in Tabanan Regency is as follows.

1. A1 : Limited number of tourists
2. A3 : Type of attraction set
3. A4 : Time duration set
4. B5 : The community prepare homestay
5. C3 : The contribution of tourism to socio-culture
6. E1 : Complementing existing facilities
7. F1 : Tourists are considered as friends and relatives
8. F2 : Tourists are introduced to the local life of the community

9. F3 : Local tourism activities offered to tourists

2.3.4. Excess Resources

This quadrant is considered less important by the community in Tista Rural Tourism, Tabanan Regency, but the resulting performance is very good. Therefore, the importance level is small and the activity is very good, so this quadrant is considered as group that is redundant in terms of resources. This excess of resources quadrant shows that the average value of each indicator of importance is lower than the overall factor value of the importance level and the average value of each performance indicator is higher than the average value of the overall factor of the performance level.

The results of the Cartesian diagram analysis in the excess of resources quadrant is the quadrant with the fewest indicators compared to the other quadrants, namely: only 4 indicators. For more details, those which is included in the excess of resources of Tista Rural Tourism as alternative tourism in Tabanan Regency are as follows.

1. A2 : Specific area settings
2. B1 : Provided local guide
3. C4 : Tourism's contribution to nature
4. F4 : Local menu offered to tourists

3. Conclusions

Based on the data collected and through analytical calculations, it was found that the average of the importance level of Tista Rural Tourism as alternative tourism in Tabanan Regency was 4.72 which can be categorized as very important. In details, in the average results are four factors that are above the highest average related to the level of importance. Those are: Positive interaction between the community and tourists (4.87; very important), Reasonable development (4.80; very important), Nature, social, culture conservation (4.78; very important), Involving the community (4.76; very important).

From the results of the analysis related to community responses, in general, the average performance of Tista Rural Tourism as alternative tourism in Tabanan Regency is 4.10 which can be categorized as good. It means that this is lower than the results of the level of importance. Generally, it can be seen that four factors scored above the average overall level of performance, such as: Involvement of the community (4.18; good), Reasonable development (4.18; good), Nature, social and culture conservation (4,13; good), Meaning and experience (4,10; good).

Identification of IPA analysis in Tista Rural Tourism is grouped into four quadrants (A/I), (B/II), (C/III), and (D/IV). It is found in the results of grouping all variables that the average importance level is 4.72 (very important) as the Y Axis and the average performance level is 4.10 (good) as the X Axis. In Quadrant A which is the main priority, there are 7 indicators (A5, C1, C5, C6, D2, D3, E2); Quadrant B as an superiority has 16 indicators (B2, B3, B4, B6, C2, C7, C8, C9, D1, D4, D5, E3, E4, E5, E6, E7); In Quadrant C is a low priority, there are 9 indicators (A1, A3, A4, B5, C3, E1, F1, F2, F3); and Quadrant D as the quadrant of excess resources has 4 indicators (A2, B1, C4, F4).

References

- Aliyah, Istijabatul. 2020. *Ecoculture Minded Tourism Village*. Surakarta: Yayasan Kita Menulis.
- Antara, Made. 2016. *Governance Guide for Kenderan Rural Tourism*. Denpasar: Pelawa Sari.
- Baiquni, M. 2010. *Sustainable Tourism in the Vortex of a Global Crisis*. Denpasar: Udayana Press.
- Butler, R.W. 1980. *The Concept of a Tourist Area Life Cycle of Evolution: Implications for Management of Resources*. Canadian Geographer.
- Fagence, Michael. 1997. *Approches to Planning for Rural and Village Tourism Realizing The Potential of Rural Areas an Village*. Proceedings on the training and workshop on Planning Sustainable Tourism, ed. Minnery, John, Gunawan Myra, P. Penerbit: ITB, Bandung.

- Harmini, AA. Ayu Ngurah, dkk. 2021. *Alternative Tourism Textbooks*. Purbalingga: CV. EUREKA MEDIA AKSARA.
- Korten, David C. 1988. *People's Dimension Development*. Jakarta: Yayasan Obor Indonesia.
- Maksimilianus, Ardiyanto, dkk. 2020. *Village Planning and Development*. Malang: Dream Litera.
- Midgley, James. 1995. *Social Welfare in a Development Perspective*. Jakarta: Bina Rena Pariwisata.
- Murphy, P.E. 1988. *Tourism: A Community Approach*. New York and London: Routledge.
- Nasikun. 1997. *Indonesia's Social System*. Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Pitana, Gde dan Gayatri, Putu G. 2005. *Sociology of Tourism*. Yogyakarta: Andi.
- Profile of Tista Village, Kerambitan District, Tabanan Regency. 2020.
- Rahardipha, Hidayat, W. dan Widiartanto, W. 2016. *Destination Branding Program Analysis of West Nusa Tenggara Province (Qualitative Descriptive Study of Rinjani Tracking Management Board in Mount Rinjani National Park)*. Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi Bisnis, 5 (1), 174-184.
- Sugiyono. 2013. *Quantitative, Qualitative, and Quantitative Research Methods, and R & D*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Suparjan & Suyatno, Hempri. 2003. *Community Development from Development to Empowerment*. Yogyakarta: Aditya Media.
- Decree of the Regent of Tabanan Number: 180/27403/HK & HAM/2016 concerning the Determination of Pokdarwis of Tista Tourism Village, Dated September 19, 2016.
- Decree of the Regent of Tabanan Number: 180/319/03/HK & HAM/2016 concerning the Determination of Tista Tourism Village, Dated October 26, 2016.
- Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 10 of 2009 concerning Tourism.